

CERTAINTY ETH's DMP

Version 0

Description

This DMP describes the data collected within the BACCHUS and CERTAINTY European Commission projects on ice nucleating particle concentrations. The data presents all reported field measurements of ice nucleating particle concentrations as a function of space, time, temperature and relative humidity. This DMP serves to manage the data that will be used as input and output of the CERTAINTY project in work package 3 and to maximize the value, accessibility, and impact of the data produced, supporting the Institute's mission in advancing atmospheric physics research activities.

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Researchers

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Organizations

ETH Zentrum Departement of Environmental Systems
Science ETH Zürich

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: CERTAINTY ETH's DMP

Description:

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Contact: Anca Hienola

2. Funding

Funding organizations: European Commission|EC

Grants: Cloud-aERosol inTeractions & their impActs IN The earth sYstem

Project: CERTAINTY

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Public

4. Templates

Descriptions

Ice Nucleation Data Base

This data will contain a collection of field observations of ice nucleating particles digitised from the literature since 1940 - present. The digitisation process and collection process was initiated during the EU project BACCHUS. The data collected is presented as a function of latitude, altitude, time, temperature and relative humidity with respect to ice and water. The instrument type used to observe the data, literature reference (for previously published data) and source for unpublished data is also reported.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

Re-used

The data recorded produced here is a harmonised file of observations published in the literature. As such the data produced here will be the first of its kind, but it is constructed from data published in the public domain by others.

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Derived or compiled

Secondary data: Data that have been cleaned up, analysed and shared by others (published or unpublished)

1.1.5 What is its format?

netcdf, txt and .CSV will all be made available.

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

10 GB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information
- To keep on record
- To make informed decisions
- To combine with other data

Data will be used to study processes, interpret observations, and constrain aerosol-cloud interactions models and model validation.

Data will also be used to develop new parameterisations for ice nucleation to be implemented in models.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

The origin of the data are publications (95%) and in some cases other data bases such as the US Department of Energy open access data bases. In each case the data that is collected will have an associated DOI (when from publications) and source (when from other databases) linked to it, to identify where it was sourced from.

The data collected as part of this project will be posted in the ETH Research Collection Repository with a persistent DOI. To be made available after data is posted.

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Education

Project partners

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

Yes

The data will be published in the ETH Research Collection and DOI will be supplied at time of publishing data in the ETH repository.

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

A DOI will be created at ETH Libraries repository.

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

The ETH research data repository supports RDA Metadata Standards as such we will use DataCite MetaData Schema. In addition to the basic Datacite metadata, several specific institutional fields are added.

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

Descriptive

We offer descriptive metadata that enriches data or information resources with detailed information about their content, context, and structure, thereby improving their findability and practical use.

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

- Registry/Catalogue
- Metadata repository

ETH's meta data can be found at <https://www.research-collection.ethz.ch>

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

INPs, aerosol , ice nucleating particles

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

ETH Zürich Research Collection

<https://www.research-collection.ethz.ch>

Provided by ETH Libraries

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

- Follows repository standards
- Details terms of use

- Has an open access content policy
- Supports retention

3.2.1.4 Add appropriate arrangements made with the repository(ies) where the described dataset will be deposited

The DOI after being created can be updated with newer versions of the data posted to the DOI. This allows continuous updates to the data as they become available but also allows for retaining older versions of the data.

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.6 Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?

ETH Research Collections provides DOIs

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Global observational data set of ice nucleating particle concentrations

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

Open, although a certain embargo period might be applied

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

Throughout the project's duration, the dataset might be subject to an embargo of up to two years. During this period, access to the data will be

restricted, but project partners can obtain access using specific tokens. Once the embargo period concludes, the dataset will become publicly available, and accessible to all under the CC BY 4.0 license.

After the data become publicly accessible, it will not be possible to identify individuals who access the data. However, during the embargo period, access is controlled through tokens that are nominally issued to specific, selected partners.

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

At ETH Repository we store the data indefinitely. We plan to continue archiving the data beyond the current project, so it will be indefinite.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

Yes. However, we will not have closed datasets

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

Direct links are provided

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

But we will store the data indefinitely.

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

Yes

The dataset will be linked with the related scientific articles and also with the input data.

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

The embargo period (if needed) is a maximum of 2 years from publication.

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

- Readme files
- Codebooks
- Analyses
- Variable definitions
- Units of measurement
- Negative results sharing

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

Input data provenance will be linked in the metadata.

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Set up of scientific and technical committee
- Data conform to format specification

A team of scientists has already been working on constructing the data since 2020. The data is still being collated and then will undergo technical checks, format checks and be transformed into the required format.

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Re-use
- Security

Indirect cost

The costs to the project for data storage are nil. This is provided by the infrastructure of ETH Libraries.

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Use of institution infrastructure

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Anca Hienola (orcid:0000-0002-9612-1477)

Leader of WP6 and the Data management of the Project CERTAINTY

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

Passwords

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?

- Data access
- Data storage
- Data transmission
- Data recovery
- Data sharing

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

Yes

7.1.2 Documentation of other procedures

All the minimum conditions listed in Science Europe Guidance Document are covered by the WP6 Open Science and Data management

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